

Table 2. Panicles/hill, panicle exertion, 1000-grain weight, and plant height of ratoon and main crops of some rice hybrids. Sukamandi, Indonesia, 1988-89 wet season.*

Hybrid, check	Panicles/hill (no.)		Panicle exertion (%)		1000-grain weight (g)		Plant height (cm)	
	Main	Ratoon	Main	Ratoon	Main	Ratoon	Main	Ratoon
V20 A/IR25912	13.5	10.00 (74)	104.05	77.65 (74)	26.13	20.07 (76)	116.0	68.6 (59)
V20 A/IR46	13.3	11.95 (89)	105.35	77.03 (73)	22.35	20.42 (92)	104.2	66.6 (64)
V20 A/IR64	12.5	9.35 (74)	105.70	85.79 (81)	28.10	20.34 (73)	111.6	71.7 (64)
V20 A/Kr. Aceh	16.4	11.25 (68)	93.00	86.99 (93)	29.15	22.64 (78)	116.6	73.5 (63)
V20 A/IR28178	13.1	8.80 (67)	109.51	80.83 (73)	26.05	20.24 (78)	113.5	64.7 (57)
V20 A/M66b	14.9	10.50 (70)	111.20	78.33 (70)	28.05	21.07 (76)	118.4	71.0 (60)
Dodokan	15.7	10.45 (66)	113.50	71.35 (63)	28.55	23.25 (82)	104.2	72.2 (69)
LSD (0.05)	3.6	3.81	7.55	2.98	5.66	6.58	3.7	3.6
CV (%)	10.4	14.7	2.9	1.5	8.7	12.9	1.3	2.1

*Figures in parentheses are % of main crop.

weight of the ratoon crop was about 76-78% of that of the main crop. Plant height ranged from 64.7 cm for V20 A/IR28178 to 73.5 cm for V20 A/Krueng-Aceh (Table 2). *Helminthosporium sigmoideum*

incidence on the hybrids was 6-50%, while that on Dodokan was only 1%. V20 A/IR25912, V20 A/IR64, and V20 A/IR28178 yielded significantly more than the check.

F₁ hybrids offer some advantages for use in the ratoon crop. In breeding programs for hybrid rice, emphasis should be given to selecting parents with good ratooning ability. ■

Yield and yield components of some new rice hybrids derived from IR58025 A and IR62829 A in Indonesia

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We evaluated 15 IRRI rice hybrids of which eight were derived from IR58025 A and seven from IR62829 A, three Indonesian hybrids derived from IR62829 A, IR64, and Way-Seputih in a yield trial during the 1991 dry season in Kuningan. Single seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing in 3- × 5-m² plots with three replications. Plots

were fertilized with 135-50-50 kg NPK/ha. IR58025 A/IR10198, IR58025 A/IR15324, and IR58025 A/Pusa 150 yielded as much as IR64 and Way-Seputih. The hybrids had more unfilled grains/panicle than IR64 (see table). ■

Yield components of some new rice hybrids. Kuningan, Indonesia, 1991 dry season.

Hybrid, variety	Yield (t/ha)	Maturity (d)	1000-grain wt (g)	Filled grains/panicle (no.)	Panicles/hill (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Plant height (cm)	Unfilled grains/panicle (no.)
IR64	5.9	135	20.41	61.11	16.9	19.8	68.9	13.42
IR58025 A/IR10198	5.9	136	21.59	81.28	16.23	20.6	77.7	24.20
IR58025 A/IR15324	5.4	127	22.61	74.33	14.96	20.3	77.1	24.81
Way-Seputih	5.2	136	22.62	88.34	12.53	16.9	77.4	24.13
IR58025 A/Pusa 150	5.2	130	21.40	79.04	15.43	18.2	74.8	36.57
IR58025 A/IR40750	5.0	141	20.24	79.97	14.9	18.2	81.3	45.46
IR62829 A/Pusa 150	4.9	127	19.43	44.19	19.4	16.6	66.0	23.5
IR58025 A/IR37839	4.7	136	21.34	63.14	16.23	19.6	78.4	23.65
IR62829 A/IR28238	4.7	127	18.02	71.18	15.2	16.5	73.9	32.70
IR62829 A/IR40750	4.5	130	19.11	46.70	19.93	17.9	67.8	28.29
IR58025 A/IR54742	4.4	143	21.92	75.90	11.23	20.4	86.0	54.15
IR62829 A/M66b	4.1	127	20.22	53.50	16.26	17.2	69.6	31.17
IR62829 A/IR15324	4.0	127	20.65	70.04	14.17	18.7	75.5	31.33
IR62829 A/IR10198	3.9	127	19.62	74.53	11.43	18.2	74.5	36.50
IR62829 A/IR54	3.4	136	21.31	39.49	19.7	18.2	67.8	32.0
IR62829 A/IR29723	1.8	130	21.50	26.02	17.13	16.0	68.4	64.55
IR62829 A/IR64	1.7	130	20.52	28.47	18.53	18.2	67.4	39.80
IR58025 A/IR29723	1.6	141	23.74	45.58	13.4	18.6	75.9	74.95
IR58025 A/IR32809	1.1	136	23.78	68.49	13.13	18.8	74.2	57.6
IR62829 A/IR32809	1.0	130	22.98	25.38	17.36	18.3	62.7	44.03
CV (%)	14.0	-	3.8	20.0	16.9	8.5	3.4	26.9
LSD (0.05)	0.9	-	1.29	15.38	4.28	2.52	4.08	16.13

An innovative approach to improve rice yield

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In areas where rice production has stagnated and demand continues to increase, new approaches are needed to stimulate production. We applied plant growth regulators (PGRs) to rice in an attempt to improve yield.

The 100-m² experimental and control plots had thirty 10-m rows with 0.2-m spacing between rows and 1-m spacing between plots, replicated three times. High-yielding PR106 seeds, treated with streptomycin and methoxy-ethyl-mercury chloride, were sown in mid-May and transplanted in late Jun. The foliar sprays of PGRs (Table 1) were applied weekly from early Aug to Oct using the manufacturers' recommended dose. The control plot was sprayed weekly with quantities of water equivalent to the recommended doses.